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Abstract:

This deliverable aims at presenting the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the DAM4CO₂ project.

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Document History

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Approval History

	Name Surname	Date of Approval
WP Leader	Alessio Fuoco	11/04/2024
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*on behalf of the EB

1. Executive Summary

The present document describes the data management plan (DMP) for the DAM4CO₂ project. The plan describes the actions that will be undertaken in the management of all data generated by the DAM4CO₂ partners during the entire lifetime of the project, and after the end of the project when needed. This document treats the aspects regarding the handling of the data during and after the project, the format and type of data, methodology employed, processing, curation, and preservation of the data¹. The plan is structured in accordance with the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template, version 1.1 from April 01, 2022 (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx) and contains the Data Summary, the guidelines to handle the data accordingly to the FAIR principle (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), other research outputs, the allocation of the resources, data security and ethical aspects. A first version of DMP is related to deliverable D1.2 and is due after 6 months from the starting of DAM4CO₂ (April 2024). Updates of the plan will be presented at month 36 or whenever needed.

2. Data Summary

During the execution of the DAM4CO₂ project, a wide range of research data will be generated through, experiments, measurements, simulations, designs, etc. The obtained data and associated metadata will be elaborated and reported in tables, reports, presentations, or any other form to be available and exploitable by all the members of the project. The most relevant information regarding the use of generated data by the partners of the project are reported in the following table.

Table 1 Data Summary for CNR

Data summary	Partner 1: CNR
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Yes, we will re-use existing literature data regarding: (i) the preparation, characterization, and modeling of membranes and to understand their transport and catalytic properties; (ii) the solid state NMR characterization of MOFs, membrane polymers, and catalysts to set experimental conditions for measurements and compare with data generated in the project.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	*.xlsx; *.docx; *.pptx; *.jpg; *.pdf; *.txt; *.tiff; *.png; *.csv; and all the formats generated by experimental set-ups and simulation tools. NMR data are generated as Bruker TopSpin and Varian SpinSight files which are accessible also with numerous commercial and open-source software packages.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The expected size of the single data will depend on the task and work-package. The full size of the data will be in the range of hundreds of gigabytes since it will include raw experimental data and their processing, simulation results, pictures, and video.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The data will be the result of observations and experiments regarding the preparation and characterization of the materials

¹European Commission Horizon 2020 Online Manual: Data Management. [Reference Source](#)

	and membranes generated in DAM4CO ₂ . The re-used data come from previous scientific publications and projects.
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The collected/generated data will be used to characterize structural properties of MOFs, catalysts, polymers and membranes produced in the project with the ultimate aim of guiding the preparation of materials with optimized properties, such as morphology, mechanical properties, transport and conversion efficiency of membranes, adsorption properties of MOFs, and conversion efficiency of catalysts. The data will be also used for validation purposes of models and for comparison with the state-of-the-art.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Our data might be useful to different kinds of audience, including academic and industrial communities. They will be of interest for those interested in membrane preparation and modelling, their characterization including transport and catalytic properties, as well as for the characterization of neat materials.

Table 2 Data Summary for INSTM

Data summary	Partner 2: INSTM
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Yes, we will re-use existing literature data regarding the preparation, characterization and adsorption and catalytic performances of polymers, metal-organic frameworks, catalysts and membranes for carbon dioxide capture and conversion.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	*.xlsx; *.docx; *.pptx; *.jpg; *.pdf; *.txt; *.tiff; *.png; *.csv; *.aif; *.opj; *.inp;. and all the raw data formats generated by experimental set-ups.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The expected size of the single data will depend on the task and work-package. The full size of the data will be in the range of tens of gigabytes since it will include raw experimental data and their processing.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The generated data will be the result of observations and characterization regarding the synthetic procedures and characterization of the materials and membranes generated in DAM4CO ₂ . The re-used data come from previous scientific publications and projects.
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The data will be useful to improve the quality and yields of adsorbents and catalysts with the desired features to be employed as fillers in the preparation of mixed matrix membranes. The data will be also useful to drive the preparation of the final membranes with the desired separation and catalytic performances.

Table 3 Data Summary for UPV

Data summary	Partner 3: UPV
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Yes, we will use data coming from peer-reviewed literature regarding to the synthesis of photocatalysts for reverse water gas shift (RWGS) and Fisher-Tropsch (FT). Also, our production efficiencies in both reactions will be compared with other researchers.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	This project will generate raw and processed data related to characterization of materials (.txt; .csv; .xlsx). Results related to photocatalytic test will generate raw data in form of chromatographic spectrums (.txt, .jpg) and additional graphics showing production efficiency for RWGS and FT (.opju; .xlsx). Interpretation of these results will generate additional data that will come in several formats such as powerpoint, word, origin and excel files. Finally we must consider a great amount of bibliographic data (.pdf; .html)
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	This point is difficult to estimate, we consider to consume at least 100 Gb.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The research will generate raw and interpreted data due to results of direct measurements and interpretation of results. Overall data will be evaluated and filtered to achieve project targets.
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The main purpose of the collected data will be to accomplish project objectives. Additionally, data of interest will be considered to be used for publications or for scientific dissemination in workshops and congresses.

Table 4 Data Summary for Primalchit

Data summary	Partner 4: PRIMALCHIT
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Yes, for the LCA, PRIMALCHIT will use existing data in two manners; by one side, PRIMALCHIT will use existing data in the literature to determine the approach to present the DAM4CO ₂ technology in terms of processes, systems and products, as required to life cycle assessment. On the other side, data bases with information about mass, wastes and energy flows for LCA will be also used.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	The project DAM4CO ₂ will generate the following types and formats of data: presentation of the results obtained will be accomplished in *.pptx; *.docx; *.pdf; *.xlsx. Images and diagrams will be presented in the reports but will be also provided in *.jpg and/or *.tiff format. Moreover, projects and data obtained during LCA implementation by means of SimaPro or OpenLCA software, will be saved in *.csv.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The expected size of the data that will be generated will range between 1-10 Gb.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The data will be the result of the work developed aimed at LCA of the DAM4CO ₂ technology. Data from data base are included in the software that PRIMALCHIT will employ.
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The purpose of the data generation is the life cycle analysis or assessment of the membrane technology or fuel production. With these data, PRIMALCHIT will determine the environmental impact of the proposed technology in the DAM4CO ₂ project.

Table 5 Data Summary for Me-Sep

Data summary	Partner 5: Me-Sep
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Yes, we plan to re-use existing literature data to develop, manufacture, and characterize membranes, as well as to develop a CFD model for the membrane module.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	*.xlsx; *.docx; *.pptx; *.jpg; *.pdf; *.txt; *.tiff; *.png; *.csv; and all the formats generated by experimental set-ups and simulation tools.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The total size of the generated data will reach several tens of gigabytes and will include raw and processed experimental data, CFD simulation results, photos, and videos.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The generated data will be a result of tasks performed in the DAM4CO ₂ project, i.e. manufacturing and characterization of membranes and developing a CFD model of the membrane module. The re-used data comes from previous scientific publication and projects.
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The accumulated/generated data are essential for understanding the phenomena and processes occurring and for early detection and implementation of modifications and improvements both in the membrane manufacturing process and in membrane module modeling. Data analysis allows for situational assessment and setting further goals, as well as identifying trends and opportunities. The collected data will also aid in evaluating the project's impact, measuring success, and implementing necessary adjustments or improvements. It also enables monitoring progress in achieving project goals.

Table 6 Data Summary for USwan

Data summary	Partner 6: USwan
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it	Literature data present in high quality peer-reviewed publications can be considered as benchmark. Any important measurements

for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	and data will be reproduced, anyway. If founds deviating too much from the literature ones the latter will be discarded and our ones kept, for consistency.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	Raw data; experimental; computed data; data associated with formal publications; interactive data; (.doc, .txt, etc.), micrographs and image data (.tiff, .jpeg, etc.), tabulation (.doc, .xlsx); Bibliographic information; visual assessment (.csv or .xlsx); Statistical tests (txt or .csv, .xlsx,r .html); Photos (.png or .jpg); PDF; etc.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	A few GBs at best
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Experimental data can be obtained from project partners or other collaborators. Generated research data will be subjected to evaluation and interpretation. Re-used data are considered the ones found in the literature, used to be compared to experimental data.
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Data produced during the project will be included into scientific articles, and/or to monitor the progress of the project activity.

Table 7 Data Summary for UEdin

Data summary	Partner 7: UEdin
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Literature data will be used for comparison with data collected in the project and assess the validity of our process,
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	We will generate simulation files (.usc), documents .doc,.pdf) and tables (.xls). Permeation experiments will generate text files and .xls files. Spectroscopic and structural analysis of monomers and polymers will generate crystal information files (.cif) and raw data in appropriate formats.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	It depends on the type of data. In the order of gigabytes.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Experimental data from permeation tests. Simulation files. Results reports and tables. Spectroscopic and structural analysis.
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its	Data will be used to characterize and assess the materials/processes proposed.

relation to the objectives of the project?	
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3. FAIR data

The FAIR principles involve a set of instructions to follow to maximize the value of the data. The purpose of this guidelines is to support the data reusability in future project and research, facilitating knowledge discovery and improving research transparency. According to the FAIR criteria the data must be **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable². To allow the interoperability, all data will be adequately commented using the appropriate ontology and vocabularies, while if it not possible, full explanation and definitions will be given. In the case of use of not original data, proper reference will be given to precisely identify of the source.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Table 8 Making Data findable for CNR

FAIR data (Making data findable)	Partner 1: CNR
Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?	Data will be stored both in our hard disks and in the collaborative spaces of the project. A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to the data when they are included in scientific publications to ensure the data are easily citable and findable. The use of Zenodo will be implemented during the execution of the project.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	Yes, keywords will be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and re-use.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	All documents, have a specific number to versions can be easily monitored during the pathway of update. When saved, the file will have a format “*_vXy” where X is a number and denotes a major change, and y is a letter and denotes a minor change (e.g. _v1a, _v1b, _v2a).
Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	Metadata will clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes. When metadata standards do not exist, we will adhere to best practices for descriptive and structured metadata in scientific research. For the data coming from characterization experiments, metadata will include all the parameters used for the acquisition and processing of the data.

Table 9 Making Data findable for INSTM

FAIR data (Making data findable)	Partner2 : INSTM
Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata,	Data will be stored both in our hard disks and in the collaborative spaces of the project. A Digital Object

² The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship <https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?	Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to the data when they are included in scientific publication to ensure the data is easily citable and findable. The use of Zenodo will be implemented during the execution of the project.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	Yes, keywords are provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and re-use.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	All documents will have a specific number so that different versions can be easily monitored. When saved, the file will have a format “*_vXy” where X is a number and denotes a major change, and y is a letter and denotes a minor change (e.g. _v1a, _v1b, _v2a).
Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes. If metadata standards do not exist, we will adhere to best practices for descriptive and structured metadata in scientific research.

Table 10 Making Data findable for UPV

FAIR data (Making data findable)	Partner 3: UPV
Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?	Data will be stored both in our hard discs and in the collaborative spaces of the project. A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to the data when they are included in scientific publication to ensure the data is easily citable and findable. Data will be indexed by dates and in independent folders by years. Tracking and traceability of these data will be easy to follow due to register files that we will keep including the date, person who did generate it, the field of data (characterization and type; photocatalysis, text document, presentation etc..) and place where it is stored. However, the relevant data will be kept in a single powerpoint file to keep a record of the most interesting findings.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	Yes
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Yes, metadata will be indexed first by year and second by photocatalyst prepared, and finally by characterization technique
Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	For our case we will use metadata related to characterization to improve photocatalytic performance. Understanding of materials properties will provide key information to enhance their catalytic activity that one of the key targets of this project.

<p>Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?</p>	<p>Data will be stored both in our hard discs and in the collaborative spaces of the project. A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to the data when they are included in scientific publication to ensure the data is easily citable and findable. Data will be indexed by dates and in independent folders by years. Tracking and traceability of these data will be easy to follow due to register files that we will keep including the date, person who did generate it, the field of data (characterization and type; photocatalysis, text document, presentation etc..) and place where it is stored. However, the relevant data will be kept in a single powerpoint file to keep a record of the most interesting findings.</p>
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Table 11 Making Data findable for Primalchit

FAIR data (Making data findable)	Partner 4: PRIMALCHIT
<p>Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?</p>	<p>Data generated by PRIMALCHIT during the LCA implementation will be stored in the company server. Moreover, they will be uploaded as a report in the project webpage and in the EC CORDIS service as a deliverable.</p>
<p>Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?</p>	<p>Yes, keywords will be assigned to each report or data sets.</p>
<p>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</p>	<p>All documents, have a specific number to versions can be easily monitored during the progression.</p>
<p>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</p>	<p>Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes. If metadata standards do not exist, we will adhere to best practices for descriptive and structured metadata in scientific research</p>

Table 12 Making Data findable for Me-Sep

FAIR data (Making data findable)	Partner 5: Me-Sep
<p>Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?</p>	<p>Data will be stored in Me-Sep server, hard discs of used equipment and in the collaborative spaces of the project.</p>
<p>Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?</p>	<p>yes</p>

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	All documents, have a specific number to versions can be easily monitored during the progression.
Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes. If metadata standards not exist we will adhere to best practices for descriptive and structured metadata in scientific research

Table 13 Making Data findable for USwan

FAIR data (Making data findable)	Partner 6: USwan
Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?	Data will be stored both on our hard disks and in the collaborative spaces of the project. A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to the data when they are included in scientific publication to ensure the data is easily citable and findable.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	Yes
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	All documents, have a specific number to versions can be easily monitored during the progression.
Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes. If metadata standards do not exist, we will adhere to best practices for descriptive and structured metadata in scientific research.

Table 14 Making Data findable for UEdin

FAIR data (Making data findable)	Partner 7 : UEdin
Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?	Yes, they will be stored in our laptops, on the private area of the project website and will be deposited in the UEDIN repository
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	Yes
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	yes
Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please	Yes

outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	
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3.2 Making data accessible

Table 15 Making Data Openly Accessible for CNR

FAIR data (Making Data Openly Accessible)	Partner 1 : CNR
Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	The data will be stored in the private section of the project website that will be hosted on CNR servers. All the people officially involved in the project will be able to access this password-protected repository. During the execution of the project, the use of Zenodo and IRIS will be implemented
Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	The used repository will depend on the characteristics of the specific data. We do not foresee any issue related to appropriate arrangement since the chosen platforms are developed under the European OpenAIRE (e.g. Zenodo) or are repositories affiliated with our institution (e.g. IRIS).
Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes
Data	
Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	The data will be made available upon publication as supporting information to the scientific article or deposited in the repositories identified above. Embargo will be applied in the case protection of the intellectual property is foreseen by one or more partners of the consortium.
If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible	Embargo will be applied for the time needed to protect the intellectual properties (e.g. data will be disclosed after a patent is filed).
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	There are no restrictions on the use of disclosed data.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	The data will be accessible upon open access principles.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	No
Metadata	
Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	The metadata will remain available for the lifetime of the repository.
Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	When possible, documentation of the software needed to read the data will be included.

Table 16 Making Data Openly Accessible for INSTM

FAIR data (Making Data Openly Accessible)	Partner 2: INSTM
Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	The project data will be stored in the private section of the project website that will be hosted on CNR servers. This will ensure a safe storage of the data and scheduled backups. All the people officially involved in the project will be able to access this password-protected repository, through the Intranet link at project website. Zenodo ed IRIS will be used during the project
Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	Yes
Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes
Data	
Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data	The data will be made available upon publication as supporting information to the scientific article or deposited in the repositories identified above. Embargo will be applied in the case protection of the intellectual property is foreseen by one or more partners of the consortium.

closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	
If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible	Embargo will be applied for the time needed to protect the intellectual properties (e.g. they will be disclosed after filing a patent).
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	There are no restrictions on the use of disclosed data.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	The data will be accessible upon open access principles.
Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	No
Metadata	
Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	The metadata will remain available for the lifetime of the repository.
Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	When possible, documentation of the software needed to read the data will be included.

Table 17 Making Data Openly Accessible for UPV

FAIR data (Making Data Openly Accessible)	Partner 3: UPV
Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	Data will be accumulated in ITQ servers and then shared with CNR coordinators to make them accessible to all partners
Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	In this project we will use platforms developed under the European OpenAIRE such as Zenodo, repository affiliated to our university and for sending files such as FileSender or RedIRIS
Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes

Data	
<p>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</p>	<p>Firstly, data will not be open available, and embargo will be applied. However, all the data will be shared with all partners to ensure project progress. Once data is processed and all profit and benefit derived from these data is achieved by the partners of the project, data could be open accessible but always with the consensus of all partners and respecting grant agreement of DAM4CO₂ project.</p> <p>However, some data will be published in form of research articles and congresses communication with the agreement of all partners. Open access journals could be promoted as well to make data derived from the project most accessible</p>
<p>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible</p>	<p>When it is valorized by the consortium the data will kept embargoed till all intellectual data is protected. Some data would be embargoed even after some time of finishing the project if it necessary. Release of all data will be subjected always to the agreement of all partners.</p> <p>Data published in scientific articles could be shared in demand of other researchers not related to this project previous authorization of coordinators.</p>
<p>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</p>	<p>Not disclosed Data could be used on demand if all partners agree after or before finishing the article. Data will be available to any researcher or general public.</p> <p>Access to our repository will be complete restricted to the project partners</p>
<p>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</p>	<p>The person who asks for specific data must contact directly with us, ensuring the identity of the person accessing to data.</p>
<p>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</p>	<p>No</p>
Metadata	
<p>Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</p>	<p>The data and metadata will kept for 5 years after project ending in our physical repository (computers, hard disk)</p>

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	Normally, metadata has an extension easy to identify which software it is necessary to open the data. Many of the metadata need specific software to treat data such as X'Pert HighScore Plus to treat XRD spectrums, that are not available in open access.
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Table 18 Making Data Openly Accessible for Primalchit

FAIR data (Making Data Openly Accessible)	Partner 4: PRIMALCHIT
Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	The data will be stored in the private section of the project website that will be hosted on CNR (coordination entity) servers. All the people officially involved in the project will be able to access this password-protected repository. During the lifetime of the project, the use of Zenodo will be implemented
Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	The used repository will depend on the characteristic of the specific data. We do not foresee any issue related to appropriate arrangement since the chosen platforms are developed under the European OpenAIRE (e.g. Zenodo).
Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes, the repository will ensure that data is assigned an identifier that will be resolved to a digital object.
Data	
Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	The data from LCA will be made openly available by means of their publication in a scientific article. Open access journals will be preferred at this purpose. Moreover, the supporting information of these publications could contain the raw data used for calculations. As mentioned before, all the data generated will be uploaded as a report to the repository in the DAM4CO ₂ webpage.
If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible	Embargo will be applied for the time needed to protect the intellectual properties (e.g. they will be disclosed after file a patent). In the case of LCA intellectual property protection will be less probable.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	There is no restriction on the use of disclosed data.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	The data will be accessible upon open access principles. Then, no ascertainment of the person accessing will be needed.
Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	No, a data access committee is not needed.
Metadata	
Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes, for DAM4CO ₂ project, metadata will be made openly available and will contain information to enable the access of the user to these data.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Metadata for DAM4CO ₂ project will remain available during the entire life span of the repository.
Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	When needed, and if possible, documentation on the software needed to read the data will be included.

Table 19 Making Data Openly Accessible for Me-Sep

FAIR data (Making Data Openly Accessible)	Partner 5 : Me-Sep
Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	The Me-Sep server will be used for data generated and/or stored during and after the project. All the people officially involved in the project will be able to access password-protected folder.
Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	N/A
Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	N/A
Data	
Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against	<p>The data will be made available upon publication as supporting information to the scientific article or deposited in the repositories identified above.</p> <p>Embargo will be applied in the case protection of the intellectual property is foreseen by one or more partners of the consortium.</p>

their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	
If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible	Embargo will be applied for the time needed to protect the intellectual properties (e.g. they will be disclosed after file a patent).
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	There are no restriction on the use of disclosed data.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	In the case of open access data no access control will be established.
Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	No
Metadata	
Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	The metadata will remain available for the life time of the repository.
Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	All the data generated will be accessible via commonly used software: MS Office, Open Office, Adobe Reader, Image Viewer, etc. If any specific software is used the necessary documentation relating to that software will be provided to facilitate access to the technical data.

Table 20 Making Data Openly Accessible for USwan

FAIR data (Making Data Openly Accessible)	Partner 6 : USwan
Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	The data will be stored in the private section of the project website that will be hosted on CNR servers. All the people officially involved in the project will be able to access this password-protected repository. In addition to the shared folder of the project, when needed the data will be deposited in the Cronfa depository at Swansea University.
Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	Yes

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes
Data	
Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	The data will be made available upon publication as supporting information to the scientific article or deposited in the repositories identified above. In addition, some of the journals already require depositing the data in their repositories. When this is required the DOI resulting from the journal will be added to the DAM4CO ₂ folder.
If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible	Embargo will be applied in the case protection of the intellectual property is foreseen by one or more partners of the consortium.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	Mainly from the authors of patents or articles.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	In the case of open access data no access control will be established. If there is any access restriction or embargo, the request will be handled via the repository management team, or via the article's authors, previous approval of DAM4CO ₂ partners.
Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	We do not foresee the need for a data access committee.
Metadata	
Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Metadata for publications and datasets will be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0 or equivalent.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	In accordance with the guidelines set by Swansea University or the chosen journal. Data will always be easily accessible via authors.
Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to	All the data generated will be accessible via commonly used software: MS Office, Open Office, Adobe Reader, Image Viewer, etc. If any specific

include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	software is used the necessary documentation relating to that software will be provided to facilitate access to the technical data.
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Table 21 Making Data Openly Accessible for UEdin

FAIR data (Making Data Openly Accessible)	Partner 7 : UEdin
Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	Yes, UEDIN provides one.
Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	Yes
Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes
Data	
Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	Data will be available upon publication as supplementary information and deposited in appropriate accessible databases (e.g. CCDC). We will follow the arrangement in the Grant Agreement to publish data shared with other partners.
If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible	This will be decided by the consortium according to the grant agreement terms.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	N/A
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Open access will not identify the person access. Restricted data will be provided only to member of the consortium,
Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	no
Metadata	
Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not,	Yes

please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	As long as the repository remains active.
Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	Yes. Some commercial software will not be made available open source.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Table 22 Making Data Interoperable for CNR

FAIR data (Making Data Interoperable)	Partner 1: CNR
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	To make sure that our data are interoperable, we will adhere to established data and metadata standards. We will use native format files of the specific instruments and software used, as well as data will be stored in *.csv or *.txt formats or other commonly used formats, such as *.pdf or *.docx for documents.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?	The most common definition of the relevant scientific community is used to the extent possible. If project specific ontologies or vocabularies will be used, they will be published in open access, and we will provide mappings.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability	As far as possible, standard vocabularies and machine-readable file formats are used when storing research data.
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes, to data generated within DAM4CO ₂ , and to datasets produced in previous projects/research.

Table 23 Making Data Interoperable for INSTM

FAIR data (Making Data Interoperable)	Partner 2: INSTM
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	To make sure that our data are interoperable, we will adhere to established data and metadata standards. We will use native format files of the specific instruments and software used, as well as data will be

	stored in *.csv or *.txt formats or other commonly-used formats, such as *.pdf or *.docx for documents.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?	The most common definition of the relevant scientific community is used to the extent possible. If project specific ontologies or vocabularies will be used, they will be published in open access, and we will provide mappings.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability	As far as possible, standard vocabularies and machine-readable file formats are used when storing research data.
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes, to data generated within DAM4CO ₂ , and to datasets produced in previous projects/research

Table 24 Making Data Interoperable for UPV

FAIR data (Making Data Interoperable)	Partner 3: UPV
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	To make sure that our data are interoperable, we will adhere to established data and metadata standards. A text file could be included in each folder explaining their content.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?	A text file could be included in each folder explaining their content. No ontologies or vocabulary will be published from our side.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability	Yes, in case of characterization data, we will include general ontology for refereeing to each technique.
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Data will refer to a specific photocatalysts that with tracking files we could easily find other existing data referred to each photocatalyst synthesized.

Table 25 Making Data Interoperable for Primalchit

FAIR data (Making Data Interoperable)	Partner 4: PRIMALCHIT
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	To make sure that data are interoperable, established data and metadata standards will be employed. Native format files for the specific instruments and software will be used, but also, data will be stored in

	*.csv or *.txt formats or other commonly used formats, such as *.pdf or *.docx for documents.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?	The most common definition of the relevant scientific community is used to the most possible extent. If project specific ontologies or vocabularies will be used, they will be published in open access, and mappings will be provided.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability	As far as it's possible, standard vocabularies and machine-readable file formats are used when storing research data.
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes, the data will include references to data generated within DAM4CO ₂ , and to datasets produced in previous projects/research.

Table 26 Making Data Interoperable for Me-Sep

FAIR data (Making Data Interoperable)	Partner 5: Me-Sep
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	We will use native format files of the specific instruments and software used, as well as data will be stored in *.csv or *.txt formats or other commonly-used formats, such as *.pdf or *.docx for documents.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?	Yes
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability	Standard vocabularies and machine-readable file formats will be used
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes, to data generated within DAM4CO ₂ , and to datasets produced in previous research.

Table 27 Making Data Interoperable for USwan

FAIR data (Making Data Interoperable)	Partner 6: USwan
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	To make sure that our data is interoperable, we will adhere to established data and metadata standards. We will use native format files of the specific instruments and software used, as well as data will be

	stored in *.xlsx, *.csv or *.txt formats or other commonly used formats, such as *.pdf or *.docx for documents.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?	The most common definition of the relevant scientific community is used to the extent possible. If project specific ontologies or vocabularies will be used, they will be published in open access and we will provide mappings.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability	As far as possible, standard vocabularies and machine-readable file formats will be used when storing research data.
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes, to data generated within DAM4CO ₂ and to datasets produced in previous projects/research.

Table 28 Making Data Interoperable for UEdin

FAIR data (Making Data Interoperable)	Partner 7: UEdin
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	We will use native format files of the specific instruments and software used, as well as data will be stored in *.xlsx, *.csv or *.txt formats or other commonly used formats, such as *.pdf or *.docx for documents.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?	Yes
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability	Yes
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes

3.4 Increase data re-use

Table 29 Increase data re-use for CNR

FAIR data (Increase data re-use)	Partner 1: CNR
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Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	Data will be freely available with publications, in order to encourage the wider possible re-use in line with the obligation set out in the GA
Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.	The data will also be available to third parties even after the project ends. However, some data may have re-use restrictions due to intellectual property rights or regulatory requirements.
Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes
Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	The data obtained during the project activity will be discussed and processed with high accuracy and attention. Particular attention will be paid on validation of the protocols to check data accuracy and integrity.
How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	As long as possible, without foreseen time limits, with a minimum time of 10 years.
Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	The research output of the DAM4CO ₂ project will also consists in research papers published in relevant conference proceedings and journal. The editors of these journal follow as well strict standards for the management of the data and offer solutions for the referencing and the access of the research data

Table 30 Increase data re-use for INSTM

FAIR data (Increase data re-use)	Partner 2: INSTM
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	Data will be freely available with publications, to encourage the wider possible re-use in line with the obligation set out in the GA
Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.	The data will also be available to third parties even after the project ends. However, some data may have re-use restrictions due to intellectual property rights or regulatory requirements.
Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes
Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	The data obtained during the project activity will be discussed and processed with high accuracy and attention. Focus will be paid on validation of the protocols to check data accuracy and integrity.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	As long as possible, without foreseen time limits, with a minimum time of 10 years.
Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	Data will be freely available with publications, to encourage the wider possible re-use in line with the obligation set out in the GA

Table 31 Increase data re-use for UPV

FAIR data (Increase data re-use)	Partner 3: UPV
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	Data used in scientific publications will be freely available. Other data could be licensed following the line of grant agreement.
Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.	If grant agreement permits and all the consortium partners agrees data could be shared.
Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes
Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	Data will be discussed by all the partners and validated before releasing them.
How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	The necessary time set on the grant agreement of the project (minimum 10 years)
Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	Data used in scientific publications will be freely available. Other data could be licensed following the line of grant agreement.

Table 32 Increase data re-use for Primalchit

FAIR data (Increase data re-use)	Partner 4: PRIMALCHIT
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	During the DAM4CO ₂ project, data produced by PRIMALCHIT will be published in scientific journal as open access publication to make the data freely available.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.	Yes, the data produced during the project implementation regarding to LCA will be usable by third parties after the end on the project. It will be a good source of information for similar studies or environmental technology assessment.
Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes, the provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards to define information sources and hypothesis accepted to reach the final result.
Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	The data obtained during the project activity of LCA will be discussed and processed with high accuracy and attention. Particular focus will be paid on validation of the protocols to check data accuracy and integrity.
How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	As long as possible, without foreseen time limits, with a minimum time of 10 years.
Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	During the DAM4CO ₂ project, data produced by PRIMALCHIT will be published in scientific journal as the open access publication to make the data freely available.

Table 33 Increase data re-use for Me-Sep

FAIR data (Increase data re-use)	Partner 5: Me-Sep
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	Data will be freely available with publications, in order to encourage the wider possible re-use in line with the obligation set out in the GA
Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.	The data will also be available to third parties even after the project ends. However, some data may have re-use restrictions due to intellectual property rights or regulatory requirements.
Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes
Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	The data obtained during the project activity will be discussed with high accuracy and attention. Particular focus will be paid on validation of the protocols to check data accuracy and integrity.
How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	As long as possible, without foreseen time limits, with a minimum time of 10 years.

<p>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.</p>	<p>Data used in presentations and on our social media will be freely available.</p>
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Table 34 Increase data re-use for USwan

<p>FAIR data (Increase data re-use)</p>	<p>Partner 6: USwan</p>
<p>Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?</p>	<p>Data will be freely available with publications, in order to encourage the wider possible re-use in line with the obligation set out in the GA.</p>
<p>Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.</p>	<p>The data will also be available to third parties even after the project ends. However, some data may have re-use restrictions due to intellectual property rights or regulatory requirements.</p>
<p>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</p>	<p>Yes.</p>
<p>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</p>	<p>The data obtained during the project activity will be reproduced, discussed and processed with high accuracy and attention. Particular focus will be paid on validation of the protocols to check data accuracy and integrity.</p>
<p>How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?</p>	<p>As long as possible, without foreseen time limits, with a minimum time of 10 years.</p>
<p>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.</p>	<p>The research output of the DAM4CO₂ project will also consist in research papers published in relevant conference proceedings and journal. The editors of these journals follow as well strict standards for the management of the data and offer solutions for the referencing and the access of the research data</p>

Table 35 Increase data re-use for UEdin

<p>FAIR data (Increase data re-use)</p>	<p>Partner 7: UEdin</p>
<p>Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?</p>	<p>Data will be made available.</p>

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.	Yes
Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes
Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	Data will be discussed with experts in the consortium.
How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	For simulations scripts, as long as software is maintained by third parties.
Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	Data will be made available.

4. Other research outputs

The partners should give appropriate inputs related to the following questions

Table 36 Other research outputs

DMP requests	Partners' Input
In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g., software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g., new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	Partner name CNR: The procedures and protocols used for membrane preparation, and in general for their management, will be described in scientific publications. The experimental conditions set up for characterization of materials by solid state NMR spectroscopy, as well as procedures employed for NMR data analysis, will be described in scientific publications. The disclosure of this information may be delayed by IP protection (e.g., file a patent).
	Partner name INSTM : The procedures and protocols used for metal-organic frameworks preparation, and for the advanced characterization of adsorbents and catalysts will be described in scientific publications. Their disclosure may be delayed by IP protection (e.g., file a patent).
	Partner name: UPV Protocol related to synthesis of materials and photocatalytic testing will be published along with research articles. Protocol of preparation of no existing and novel catalyst would kept restricted by possible patents. Other relevant information as photocatalytic reactors or other information restricted to intellectual property would get restricted to ITQ-UPV

	<p>Partner name: PRIMALCHIT The methodologies selected for LCA, as well as the hypothesis for the selection, together with the results will be published in scientific journals and presented in workshops, conferences, and related forums. A protocol correlating the environmental impact methodology with the technology on study could be also developed.</p>
	<p>Partner name: Me-Sep The procedures and protocols used for membrane preparation, and in general for their management, will be presented in workshops and conferences. Their disclosure may be delayed by IP protection (e.g., file a patent).</p>
	<p>Partner name: USwan The procedures and protocols used for polymers preparation, characterization and for their management, will be described in scientific publications. Their disclosure may be delayed by IP protection (e.g., file a patent).</p>
	<p>Partner name: UEdin Software produced and simulations will be stored in the repository. Physical samples will be stored in an appropriate environment for stability, safety and accessibility.</p>
<p>Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	<p>Partner name: CNR If the need arises to protect intellectual property in the context of membrane preparation procedures and protocols, the necessary steps will be taken. The methods/protocols will be in the public domain compatibly with the patent request procedure. Any change in the methods/protocols will also be updated and disclosed.</p>
	<p>Partner name: INSTM If the need arises to protect intellectual property in the context of metal-organic frameworks preparation, and of the advanced characterization of adsorbents and catalysts, the necessary steps will be taken. The methods/protocols will be in the public domain compatibly with the patent request procedure. Any change in the methods/protocols will also be updated and disclosed.</p>
	<p>Partner name: UPV Protection of intellectual property in the context of non-existing photocatalyst could be done. The methods/protocols will be in the public domain compatibly with the patent request procedure.</p>
	<p>Partner name: PRIMALCHIT Protocols and methodologies related to LCA, as well as results obtained by PRIMALCHIT, will be available for re-use by their publication in open access and presentation in forums, conferences and webinars. For example, webinars that will take place in the framework of the communication actions of the project portfolio.</p>

	<p>Partner name: Me-Sep</p> <p>If the need arises to protect intellectual property in the context of membrane preparation procedures and protocols, the necessary steps will be taken. The methods/protocols will be in the public domain compatibly with the patent request procedure. Any change in the methods/protocols will also be updated and disclosed.</p>
	<p>Partner name: USwan</p> <p>If the need arises to protect intellectual property in the context of polymers synthesis and characterization, preparation procedures and protocols, the necessary steps will be taken. The methods/protocols will be in the public domain depending on the patent request procedure. Any change in the methods/protocols will also be updated and disclosed.</p>
	<p>Partner name: UEdin</p> <p>other research outputs will be treated in the same way.</p>

5. Allocation of resources

The data are stored in a repository located in the private section of the project website (www.dm4co2.eu). The website is hosted on the CNR servers, and the domain will active also after the end of the project to enable the accessibility of public reports, deliverables and data. For restricted documents, the access to the “members area” of the website is protected by username and passwords. When an important document was uploaded to repository the members they will be notified via a notification email. For daily exchange of data and information, or for documents under preparation, the preferred channel will be a team collaboration application to avoid parallel versions of the same document. The application will be provided by the coordinator by considering the applications available in his organization.

The partners should give appropriate inputs related to the following questions

Table 37 Allocations of resources

DMP requests	Partners' Input
<p>What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? How will these be covered?</p>	<p>Partner name: CNR</p> <p>Cost for data storage and open access publications have been already foreseen and covered with the available project budget, or sustained by CNR (e.g., cloud services, IRIS)</p>
	<p>Partner name: INSTM</p> <p>Cost for data storage and open access publications have been already foreseen and covered with the available project budget.</p>
	<p>Partner name : UPV</p>

	<p>Cost for data storage and open access publications have been already considered project budget.</p> <p>Partner name: PRIMALCHIT Cost for data storage and open access publications have been already foreseen and will be covered with the available project budget or sustained by PRIMALCHIT.</p> <p>Partner name: Me-Sep Costs for data storage have been already foreseen and covered with the available project budget, or sustained by Me-Sep (e.g., cloud services, server purchase)</p> <p>Partner name: USwan Cost for data storage and open access publications have been already foreseen and covered with the available project budget, or sustained by Swansea University (e.g., Cronfa).</p> <p>Partner name: UEdin Cost for data storage and open access publications have been already foreseen and covered with the available project budget, or sustained by University of Edinburgh</p>
<p>How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)</p>	<p>Partner name: CNR Costs for open access publications have been foreseen. The eligibility of costs for open access publications will be considered.</p>
	<p>Partner name: INSTM Costs for open access publications have been foreseen. The eligibility of costs for open access publications will be considered.</p>
	<p>Partner name: UPV Cost related to publication in open access, congresses communication are already considered in the project budget.</p>
	<p>Partner name: PRIMALCHIT As mentioned above, costs for open access publication, and webpage and server maintenance have already been foreseen and are part of the eligible costs requested in the project proposal.</p>
	<p>Partner name: Me-Sep N/A</p>
	<p>Partner name: USwan Swansea University has many Open Access deals in place with all the major publishers. If something is not covered, alternative journals will be proposed.</p>
	<p>Partner name: UEdin free University repository</p>
	<p>Partner name: CNR Everybody involved in any activities of the project is primarily responsible for their own data management. Marcello Monteleone (Data Manager) and Alessio Fuoco (project coordinator) will provide supervision.</p>
<p>Partner name: INSTM</p>	

	<p>Everybody involved in any activities of the project is primarily responsible for their own data management. Valentina Crocellà will provide supervision.</p>
	<p>Partner name: UPV Any researcher involved in the project has to take care of the data that generates and keep them in the repository. The data manager will be Herme García Baldoví</p>
	<p>Partner name: PRIMALCHIT Everybody involved in the project, will be responsible for their own data management. In particular, regarding LCA scientists in charge of its development will be in charge of data management, supervised by the team leader.</p>
	<p>Partner name: Me-Sep Everybody involved in any activities of the project is primarily responsible for their own data management. Patrycja Turalska and Krzysztof Trzaskus will provide supervision</p>
	<p>Partner name: USwan Whoever is involved in any activities of the project is primarily responsible for their own data management. For USwan it will be Mariolino Carta or C. Grazia Bezzu.</p>
	<p>Partner name: UEdin Maria-Chiara Ferrari</p>
<p>Are the resources for long-term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?</p>	<p>Partner name: CNR Data conservation in the project will be ensured through secure archiving backup systems in compliance with conservation standards. The data will be retained for a substantial period, typically a minimum of 10 years after project completion. Data with high scientific value will be stored indefinitely</p>
	<p>Partner name: INSTM Data conservation in the project will be ensured through secure archiving backup systems in compliance with conservation standards. The data will be retained for a substantial period, typically a minimum of 10 years after project completion. Data with high scientific value will be stored indefinitely</p>
	<p>Partner name: UPV Yes, everything it is covered with the project budget.</p>
	<p>Partner name: PRIMALCHIT Data conservation in the project will be ensured through secure archiving backup systems in compliance with conservation standards. The data will be retained for a substantial period, typically a minimum of 10 years after project completion. Data with high scientific value will be stored indefinitely.</p>
	<p>Partner name: Me-Sep Data conservation in the project will be ensured through secure archiving backup systems in compliance with conservation</p>

	standards. The data will be retained for a substantial period, typically a minimum of 10 years after project completion. Data with high scientific and research value will be stored indefinitely
	Partner name: USwan Data conservation in the project will be ensured through secure archiving backup systems in compliance with conservation standards. The data will be retained for a substantial period, typically a minimum of 10 years after project completion. Data with high scientific value will be stored indefinitely, and always accessible through papers' authors.
	Partner name: UEdin Yes

6. Data security

The co-worker involved in research have the care of the manage the safety of the proper data. Data in electronic format are be keep in personal computer protected by personal password of the member of the consortium, making backup copies. In order to guarantee the safety of the data the co-worker will ensure that the following instructions are observed: to avoid the loss of the date they will be stored in at least in two different device, the file will be named with precis criteria in order to ensure the progression an the tracking of the datasets, while will be minimized the use of flash memory.

The partners should give appropriate inputs related to the following questions

Table 38 Data security

DMP requests	Partners' Input
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	Partner name: CNR Data will be stored in multiple locations to prevent data loss, and cloud services with be used. The use of flash drives will be limited and used only to transfer a copy of the file.
	Partner name: INSTM Data will be stored in multiple locations to prevent data loss, and cloud services will be used. The use of flash drives will be limited and used only to transfer a copy of the file. Where possible, remote access to specific data folders in computers connected to experimental apparatus will be set up to facilitate data transfer.
	Partner name: UPV If the computer where it stored get damaged, hard disk will be kept. More than one copy of all the data will be keep just in case
	Partner name: PRIMALCHIT

	Data will be stored in multiple locations to prevent data loss, and cloud services will be used. The use of flash drives will be limited and used only to transfer a copy of the file.
	Partner name: Me-Sep Data will be stored in multiple locations to prevent data loss. The use of flash drives will be limited and used only to transfer a copy of the file.
	Partner name: USwan Data will be stored in multiple locations to prevent data loss, and cloud services will be used (i.e., OneDrive, Dropbox etc.). The use of flash drives will be limited and used only to transfer a copy of the file.
	Partner name: UEdin Data store in University repository
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Partner name: CNR Yes, the data will be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation.
	Partner name: INSTM Yes, the data will be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation.
	Partner name: UPV Yes, data will be stored in hard disk and keep is multiple places
	Partner name: PRIMALCHIT Yes, data from LCA will be stored in trusted repositories of the DAM4CO ₂ project for long-term preservation.
	Partner name: Me-Sep Yes, the data will be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation
	Partner name: USwan Yes, the data will be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation.
	Partner name: UEdin Yes

7. Ethics

The personal data will be collected in relation to the participation of project meeting workshop etc, comply with the principles of purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality. All personal data are retained with the scope of delivering the service

and the project follows the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 – general data protection regulation (GDPR)³.

The partners should give appropriate inputs related to the following questions

Table 39 Ethics

DMP requests	Partners' Input
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).</p>	<p>Partner name: CNR No</p>
	<p>Partner name: INSTM No</p>
	<p>Partner name: UPV No</p>
	<p>Partner name: PRIMALCHIT No, PRIMALCHIT has not identified any legal or ethical issue that can impact LCA data sharing.</p>
	<p>Partner name: Me-Sep No</p>
	<p>Partner name: USwan No</p>
	<p>Partner name: Uedin No</p>
<p>Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>	<p>Partner name: CNR No</p>
	<p>Partner name: INSTM No</p>
	<p>Partner name: UPV No</p>
	<p>Partner name: PRIMALCHIT No, an informed consent will not be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data for data sharing and long-term preservation.</p>
	<p>Partner name: Me-Sep No</p>
	<p>Partner name: USwan No</p>
	<p>Partner name: Uedin No</p>

³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

References

1. European Commission Horizon 2020 Online Manual: Data Management. [Reference Source](#)
2. *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*
<https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
3. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

Consortium of DAM4CO₂

Number	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
1	COO	CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT	999979500
2	BEN	INSTM	CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO NAZIONALE PER LA SCIENZA E TECNOLOGIA DEI MATERIALI	IT	999991237
3	BEN	UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	999864846
4	BEN	PRIMALCHIT	PRIMALCHIT SOLUTIONS	ES	892236168
5	BEN	Me-Sep	ME-SEP SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA	PL	887256382
6	BEN	USwan	SWANSEA UNIVERSITY	UK	999862033
7	BEN	UEdin	THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	UK	999974941

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